

Teacher's Roles in Developing Entrepreneurial Skills

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Abstract

The goal of education is entrepreneurship that is the making of an individual who is self-reliant and self-sufficient. The quality of any system of education also depends on the calibre of teachers who teach students or people in order to acquire one skill or the other. Entrepreneurial education has achieved little success due to inadequate preparation of teachers. This paper therefore attempts to look into teacher's roles in developing entrepreneurial skills in Nigeria. Teacher's challenges are examined and possible solution proffered.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, teachers, National education goals, self reliance.

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Introduction

Education is considered an important tool for attaining the national goal. It is given high regard as stated in National Policy of Education (2004) in Nigeria. One of the National education goals is the "acquisition of appropriate skills and the development of mental, physical and social abilities and competencies as equipment for the individual to live and contribute to the development of the society. Education therefore provides learners with basic skills needed for self reliance, and to achieve this, qualified teachers are needed to impart these skills.

Overview of Entrepreneurship

The concept of entrepreneur had been viewed by different authors. Sahlman (1987) viewed an entrepreneur as somebody who introduces something new in the economy. It is the ability to create and build something from practically nothing. Stevenson and Sahlman (1987) defined it as the relentless pursuit of

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opportunity without regard to the resources currently controlled. Kourilsky (1995) opines that the entrepreneurship is characterized by three attributes: opportunity, recognition, marshalling of resources and the creation of a business.

Curriculum developers have moved from foreign domination in terms of the content we learn. Our education has shifted from the acquisition of theoretical knowledge bringing in the era of skill acquisition through entrepreneurship. They are skills that empower students to manage their business. That is why teachers whose role is to develop the economy through entrepreneurship cannot be relegated to the background and their input need to be taken seriously.

The Challenges of Teaching Profession

Teachers are facilitators of learning. They help learners (of different ages) develop their talents, entrepreneurial skills and fulfill their potential so as to have knowledge and skills to be confident people and workers. Cedefop (2005) said more demands are being placed in teachers because of the changing models of education and training system with increased attention on the outcomes of learning processes. Teachers also provide learners key competencies such as basic skills in entrepreneur, communication and sciences. Cedefop (2005) further mentioned tasks expected of teachers which include:

*Participating in school curricula design

*Designing suitable method for assessing learning outcomes rather than merely verifying that knowledge presented during the course has been assimilated

*Using new teaching methods which leave more room for different learning styles and where the imparting of knowledge is no longer the only objective.

Teachers and trainers are also faced with societal changes as today's society is becoming more and more diverse in terms of ethnic, religious and cultural background. Teachers and trainers have important role to play in overcoming prejudice and segregation and enhancing the integration of disadvantaged groups.

Population growth is one of the major factors for shortage of teachers. The shortage occurs mostly in subjects where skilled professionals are needed like Vocational studies, Information Technology, Languages etc. The profession is

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also gender sensitive. Seventy percent of teachers in both primary and secondary schools are women- showing that teaching is not seen as a career option for men.

Introduction of new subjects different from what teachers are used to is another challenge, coupled with changes to the National Policy of Education. The following must be given adequate attention for our country to achieve her goals

Research Development: Lassa (1995) pointed out that the dynamism in instructional methodologies and innovation in teachers' preparation strategies, coming at the heels of technological advancement and continuous research in Western countries, make it almost mandatory that teachers must engage in research in order to keep abreast of new development. Factors responsible for lack of research include technical know-how on the part of teachers, lack of funds and research grants and lack of access to current literature.

In-Service Training: Training is necessary for teachers to update themselves. Mohammed *et al.* (2002) described in-service training as that part of organized learning experience provided to teachers after appointment designed to develop understanding of work operations standards, institution, philosophy, policies and procedures as well as current research result. Teachers learn new methods approaches, techniques etc in teaching after the training. Also, those who lack professional qualifications register and update their knowledge.

Provision of Local Instructional Materials: Mohammed *et al.* (2002) refers to it as arrays of stimulus which are provide to facilitate learning. Funds should be made available to purchase locally made materials and books which is more comprehensive than foreign materials and books.

Payment of Salaries and Allowances: Attention should be given to prompt payment of teachers' salaries and allowances. Teachers need appropriate remuneration. Gone are the days when people say teachers' reward is in heaven. This calls for the payment of a living wage that commensurate with the duties teachers perform considering their relevance. Youths in choosing career opt for other profession due to poor remuneration and how income status accorded to teaching profession. This was buttressed that the best and thanks brightest have followed the brain drain to work in more fulfilling institutions. Some good teachers cross the carpet into other sectors but nobody from the other sectors is willing to peep into teaching profession.

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Provision of Infrastructural Facilities: Infrastructural facilities are physical and spatial enablers of teaching and learning e.g. classrooms, laboratories, power supply, equipment, libraries etc. Unfortunately, most schools lack these amenities; where they exist, it is either they are not functioning because of lack of skilled teachers or their infrastructure is on bad condition. Overpopulated classroom, dilapidated buildings, absence of power etc are some of the obstacles to good teaching-learning atmosphere for teachers and students.

Conclusion

Education has the ability to change and reform individuals, and in so doing helps develop a perspective in which individuals view life in a way to make it better. Teachers are the driving force behind education and entrepreneurship: Adenipekun (2008) reports that skills that many entrepreneurs learn on the streets could be learnt in the classroom. Enabling entrepreneurial skills to be taught in the classroom would allow students to have and manage businesses of their own and as a result, there had be a decrease in the unemployment rate. The inculcation of these skills can be done by a well trained teacher and should be encouraged by the government.

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